

MOLECULAR PHYSIOLOGY AND GENETICS

METHOD OF TARGETED PREPARATION OF HARD DENTAL TISSUES USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

Gurskaya N.,

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant

Rustamov E.,

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant

Ashrafov D.

Department of Orthopedic Dentistry, Assistant

Azerbaijan Medical University

Baku, Azerbaijan

Abstract

At the moment, the problem of human congenital pathology remains relevant. Hereditary changes also manifest themselves in the maxillofacial region, in particular expressed as a violation of the structure of dental tissues [4, 5]. Dentinogenesis imperfecta is one of the most well-known forms of hereditary anomalies of dentin formation. This disease occurs with a frequency of about 1:8000 people [1].

Keywords: dentinogenesis, root canal obstruction, digital technologies.

The clinical picture of dentinogenesis imperfecta is very characteristic. Teeth are of normal size and shape and erupt in the middle period. The color intensity varies - most often watery-gray with a pearlescent sheen or a brown tint. Soon after the tooth erupts, the enamel chips off, and its remains have sharp edges. Progressive wear of the enamel and a decrease in the height of the teeth and their volume are possible. Exposed dentin wears off quickly; it is 1.5 times softer than normal. Complaints of pain are usually not from hyperesthesia, but from trauma to the gums, due to abrasion of the crowns of the teeth or trauma to the tongue and lips from the sharp edges of the teeth. The specificity of the clinical manifestations of dentinogenesis imperfecta, in particular the obstruction of the root canals, necessitates a qualified dentist's approach to the treatment of this pathology. When treating patients with dentinogenesis imperfecta, significant difficulties are caused by the lack of the possibility of full endodontic intervention due to obliteration of the pulp chamber and root canals. Obliteration of the canals entails the need to artificially create a bed for the LCS. Due to the fact that the "blind" production of a canal for LCS is fraught with complications in the form of perforation of the tooth root, we proposed a method of tooth preparation using modern 3D modeling technology and the production of a 3D template.

The purpose of the study is to optimize the treatment of patients with dentinogenesis imperfecta.

Material and methods.

We made a phantom model with a tooth in which the root canals are impassable. The model is a complete removable laminar denture, in which the removed tooth 25 is installed in the artificial tooth. A silicone impression was taken from the previously made phantom model, and a plaster model was cast. The next step was to fabricate an x-ray template containing an embedded Lego brick and metal pellets needed as reference points to calibrate the CNC machine settings. An analogue for further actions was the method of using surgical templates for dental implantation obtained using computer planning [2], however, the orientation of the axis and depth of preparation in the MGUIDE computer pro-

gram was carried out not in bone structures, as for dental implantation, but in the hard tissues of the tooth. The x-ray template was installed on the phantom model, and a computed tomography scan was performed with recording in DICOM format. The MGUIDE computer program was used to orient the axis of direction and depth of tooth preparation. The next step was to send information about the direction of the axis and the depth of preparation to the MIS center in order to obtain a program for a numerically controlled milling machine that positions the guide sleeve, which sets the axis and depth of tooth preparation. After installing the guide sleeve, the hard tissues of the tooth were prepared using an orthopedic template. The preparation was performed using a contra-angle handpiece and a custom-made steel bur with a stop, matching the length of the drills from the MGUIDE surgical kit, but having a cross-sectional diameter of 1 mm.

Results. We have developed a method for targeted preparation of hard dental tissues. After applying the orthopedic template, it was established that there was no radiological or visual perforation of the tooth root.

Conclusion.

The technique we have developed allows us to reduce the number of complications and increase the quality of treatment for patients with dentinogenesis imperfecta.

References

1. Akulenko L.V. i dr. Medicinskaja i klinicheskaja genetika dlja stomatologov. Uchebnoe posobie. Pod red. Janushevicha O.O. M.: GJeOTAR-Media; 2008.
2. De Almeida, et al. Computer-guided surgery in implantology: review of basic concepts. *J Craniofac Surg.* 2010;21(6):1917-1921.
3. Hart PS, Hart TC. Disorders of human dentin. *Cells Tissues Organs.* 2007;186:70-77. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000102682>
4. Kim JW, Simmer JP. Hereditary dentin defects. *J Dent Res.* 2007;86:392-399.
5. Maciejewska I, Chomik E. Hereditary dentine diseases resulting from mutations in DSPP gene. *J Dent.* 2012;40:542-548.